

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF NONLINEAR RESPONSE ON FIBROUS COMPOSITE

Yanchao Wang, Zheng-Ming Huang^{*2}

¹Department of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University
No.1239, Siping Road, Yangpu District, Shanghai, China
Email: 1008wangyanchao@tongji.edu.cn

² Department of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University
No.1239, Siping Road, Yangpu District, Shanghai, China
Email: huangzm@tongji.edu.cn

Keywords: Composite, Micro-mechanics, Bridging model, Nonlinear behavior, Interphase

ABSTRACT

Fibrous composites have been widely used in engineering due to their high moduli and strength to weight ratios and tailorability in material behaviors. However, it is still not easy to estimate nonlinear behavior of a fibrous composite at a micro mechanics level. Bridging Model has been proven effective in predicting elastic, plastic and strength behaviors of a composite. The model can be regarded as a simplified form of Mori-Tanaka's method in an elastic range. In this paper, an instantaneous bridging tensor is derived on basis of the incremental Mori-Tanaka method and Prandtl-Reuss plastic flow law. Nonlinear properties of several typical unidirectional composites with perfect fiber/matrix interface bonding are evaluated with this approach. Results are compared with those predicted upon the Bridging Model and with experimental data. Useful conclusions have been drawn. Furthermore, an equivalent fiber method was employed in this paper to deal with a composite with an interphase between the fiber and matrix, in which the fiber and the interphase are considered as an equivalent fiber whose effective moduli can be obtained by a two-phase micromechanics model. Then effective properties of composite consisted of matrix and equivalent fiber can be evaluated once more by the same or even a different model. Closed-form formulas for inelastic analysis of a composite with an interphase are obtained by using the Mori-Tanaka's and Bridging Model approaches. Effects of interphase properties on nonlinear behavior of composites are investigated numerically.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research attention has been increasingly paid on composite materials for their high moduli and strength to weight ratios and tailorability in material behaviours. How to predict the mechanical properties especially the ultimate strength of a composite material under different exterior loads plays a dominant role in composites involved design and application. Plenty of seminal work has been done to do the prediction, such as the well known Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method and Mori-Tanaka approach. Bridging model proposed by Huang [1] in 2001 has been proven to be accurate enough to evaluate both the linear and nonlinear response including ultimate strength of fibrous composites. The key to the bridging model is a bridging tensor, which links averaged stresses of matrix and fiber. Incorporating with classical mean field homogenization method, the compliance tensor of a composite can be expressed as a function of constituent material parameters, geometric parameters and the bridging tensor. In other words, once the bridging tensor is determined, both the elastic properties of a composite and the inner stresses of each phase can be calculated easily. Elements of the bridging tensor were first obtained by Huang with series expansion method, which can be seen as a simplified form of Mori-Tanaka method in elastic range with a higher prediction accuracy in general [2-4].

Out of elastic analysis, it has been known that a fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite experiences significant nonlinear deformation before failure, especially when subjected to transverse

compression or in-plan shear loads. In general, the constituent fiber can be treated as linear elastic until rupture while the plastic behaviour of constituent matrix is seen to make great contribution to the whole nonlinear deformation of a composite. In this paper, an instantaneous bridging tensor is derived on basis of the incremental Mori-Tanaka method. It is noted that in each load step, the constituent materials can be seen as linear elastic, therefore the formulation of instantaneous bridging tensor keeps unchanged. Only the elastic mechanical parameters of matrix materials should be replaced by plastic ones which can be obtained by Prandtl-Reuss theory. Besides, special attention should be paid on transverse ultimate strength prediction as it is frequently observed in experiments that a composite always fails before a significant nonlinear deformation happens under a transverse tension [5]. Thus a concept of stress concentration factor was employed in this paper to deal with this problem. Nonlinear responses of several typical unidirectional composites are evaluated and comparison between predicted results and experimental data is made.

Furthermore, the existence of interphase has been observed by many experiments, whose effects on composite properties are not ignorable. However, the bridging model (also called two-phase bridging model) mentioned above is established on basis of perfect interface assumption. In this paper, an equivalent fiber method was employed, in which the fiber and the interphase are considered as an equivalent fiber whose effective moduli can be obtained by a two-phase bridging model. Then effective properties of composite consisted of matrix and equivalent fiber can be evaluated once more by the same model. It has been shown in our previous work that the predicted results of the equivalent fiber method are accurate enough compared with the exact solution of a three-phase model. Effects of interphase properties on nonlinear behaviour of composites are investigated numerically.

2 BRIDGING MODEL

2.1 Two-phase bridging model

Figure 1: RVE of a UD composite

Consider a representative volume element (RVE) of a composite as shown in Figure 1. The averaged incremental stresses in matrix material and fiber can be connected by a non-singular tensor $[A_{ij}]$, the instantaneous bridging tensor, through

$$\{d\sigma_i^m\} = [A_{ij}]\{d\sigma_j^f\} \quad (1)$$

Incorporated with fundamental mean field formulations of stresses and strains shown in Equations (2)-(3) and constitutive Equations (4-6), the compliance tensor of a composite can be obtained in Equation (7).

$$\{d\sigma_i\} = V^f \{d\sigma_i^f\} + V^m \{d\sigma_i^m\} \quad (2)$$

$$\{d\varepsilon_i\} = V^f \{d\varepsilon_i^f\} + V^m \{d\varepsilon_i^m\} \quad (3)$$

$$\{d\varepsilon_i\} = [S_{ij}]\{d\sigma_j\} \quad (4)$$

$$\{d\varepsilon_i^m\} = [S_{ij}^m] \{d\sigma_i^m\} \quad (5)$$

$$\{d\varepsilon_i^f\} = [S_{ij}^f] \{d\sigma_i^f\} \quad (6)$$

$$[S_{ij}] = (V^f[S_{ij}^f] + V^m[S_{ij}^m][A_{ij}])(V^f[I] + V^m[A_{ij}])^{-1} \quad (7)$$

In this paper, $\{d\sigma_i\} = \{d\sigma_{11}, d\sigma_{22}, d\sigma_{33}, d\sigma_{23}, d\sigma_{13}, d\sigma_{12}\}^T$ and $\{d\varepsilon_j\} = \{d\varepsilon_{11}, d\varepsilon_{22}, d\varepsilon_{33}, 2d\varepsilon_{23}, 2d\varepsilon_{13}, 2d\varepsilon_{12}\}^T$, $[S_{ij}]$ denotes the instantaneous compliance tensor and a volume fraction is characterized by V . The superscripts f and m of a quantity represent corresponding parameters of constituent fiber and matrix and that without any super/subscript refers to a composite. For example, $[S_{ij}]$, $[S_{ij}^f]$ and $[S_{ij}^m]$ denote instantaneous compliance tensors of a composite, the fiber and matrix, respectively. $[I]$ is a unit tensor. It can be seen from Equation (4) that once the bridging tensor $[A_{ij}]$ is determined, the compliance tensor of a composite can be obtained easily.

A way to determine the bridging tensor is Mori-Tanaka approach together with equivalent inclusion method, which is given below. More details can be found in Ref. [6].

$$[A_{ij}] = [C_{ik}^m]([L_{kq}] + [L_{kl}][S_{lp}^m]([C_{pq}^f] - [C_{pq}^m]))[S_{ij}^f] \quad (8)$$

where $[C_{ik}^m]$ and $[C_{pq}^f]$ are the instantaneous stiffness tensors of matrix and fiber, respectively. $[L_{kl}]$ is an Eshelby's tensor. In plastic range, the instantaneous stiffness or compliance tensor of the matrix must be recalculated in each incremental step on basis of a suitable flow-rule theory. In this paper, the Prandtl-Reuss theory was employed. In the scheme of Prandtl Reuss theory, the elastic-plastic compliance tensor of the matrix material is given as

$$[S_{ij}^m] = \begin{cases} [S_{ij}^m]^e, & \text{when } \tau_0^m \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \sigma_Y^m \\ [S_{ij}^m]^e + [S_{ij}^m]^\rho, & \text{when } \tau_0^m > \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3} \sigma_Y^m \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$[S_{ij}^m]^\rho = \frac{1}{2M_T(\tau_0^m)^2} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma'_{11} \sigma'_{11} & \sigma'_{22} \sigma'_{11} & \sigma'_{33} \sigma'_{11} & 2\sigma'_{23} \sigma'_{11} & 2\sigma'_{13} \sigma'_{11} & 2\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{11} \\ \sigma'_{22} \sigma'_{22} & \sigma'_{33} \sigma'_{22} & 2\sigma'_{23} \sigma'_{22} & 2\sigma'_{13} \sigma'_{22} & 2\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{22} & \\ & \sigma'_{33} \sigma'_{33} & 2\sigma'_{23} \sigma'_{33} & 2\sigma'_{13} \sigma'_{133} & 2\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{22} & \\ & & 4\sigma'_{23} \sigma'_{23} & 4\sigma'_{13} \sigma'_{23} & 4\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{23} & \\ & & & 4\sigma'_{13} \sigma'_{13} & 4\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{13} & \\ & & & & 4\sigma'_{12} \sigma'_{12} & \end{bmatrix}_{\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma'_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

Symmetry

$$M_T^m = \frac{E^m E_T^m}{E^m - E_T^m} \quad (11)$$

where σ'_{ij} is the partial stress tensor defined as

$$\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}(\sigma_{ii})\delta_{ij}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \quad \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0, & i \neq j \\ 1, & i = j \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The octahedral shear stress in (9) and (10) is defined as

$$\tau_0^m = \left[\frac{1}{3} \sigma'_{ij} \sigma'_{ij} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13)$$

E_T^m in Equation (8) is a hardening modulus of the matrix which can be obtained from uniaxial experiment data.

2.2 Three-phase bridging model

Equations (1) – (7) were established on the assumption of a perfect interface. In other words, both the displacements and stress components at the interface of the fiber and matrix are treated as

continuous. However, on one hand, an interphase is often observed by experiments when chemical reaction occurs between constituent materials or artificial coating is added in between the constituent fiber and matrix to enhance some special physical properties. On the other hand, an interface defect is seen frequently when a composite is subjected to an impact or cyclic fatigue load. Therefore a three-phase bridging model must be established. Fortunately, many reports in the literature point out that an imperfect interface can be treated as an interphase as long as given a reasonable definition for the interphase parameters. Only an interphase model is discussed in this paper. The exact solution for three-phase bridging tensors is too complicated to be expressed explicitly, thereby needing an approximated solution in which an equivalent fiber method is employed.

Figure 2: Schematic of Equivalent Fiber Method

First, as shown in Figure 2, take the fiber and interphase as an inner-composite (referred to as equivalent fiber at next step) whose effective elastic moduli can be calculated from a two-phase bridging model.

$$E_{11}^{ef} = \frac{1}{S_{11}^{ef}}, E_{22}^{ef} = E_{33}^{ef} = \frac{1}{S_{22}^{ef}}, G_{12}^{ef} = G_{13}^{ef} = \frac{1}{S_{66}^{ef}}, G_{23}^{ef} = \frac{1}{S_{44}^{ef}}, \mu_{12}^{ef} = \mu_{13}^{ef} = \frac{-S_{12}^{ef}}{S_{11}^{ef}}, \mu_{23}^{ef} = \frac{-S_{23}^{ef}}{S_{22}^{ef}} \quad (14)$$

where S_{ij}^{ef} is the compliance tensor of the inner-composite derived from Equations (7) and (8) by replacing parameters of matrix with those of interphase. The superscript ef represents quantities of the composite (equivalent fiber).

Then, take the equivalent fiber and the matrix as an outer-composite whose mechanical properties can be obtained from Equations (7) and (8) again by replacing parameters of the fiber with those of the equivalent fiber.

3 FAILURE CRITERIA

Many classical failure criteria have been proposed to predict the failure strength of a material, such as the Maximum Normal Stress Theory, the Maximum Normal Strain Theory and Von-Mises Theory. However, predicted results might be questionable when a material is subjected to equibiaxial or equitriaxial tension or compression. Thus, a generalized maximum normal stress theory is applied.

When the sum of three normal stresses $\sigma_I + \sigma_{II} + \sigma_{III} > 0$, the stress state can be treated as equivalent tension. In that case, a tension criterion is given by

$$\sigma_{eq} \geq \sigma_u \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_{eq} = \begin{cases} \sigma_I, & \text{when } \sigma_{III} < 0 \\ [(\sigma_I)^2 + (\sigma_{II})^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}, & \text{when } \sigma_{III} = 0 \\ [(\sigma_I)^2 + (\sigma_{II})^2 + (\sigma_{III})^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}, & \text{when } \sigma_{III} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

If $\sigma_I + \sigma_{II} + \sigma_{III} < 0$, the stress state can be seen as equivalent compression in which a compression

criterion follows

$$\sigma_{eq} \leq -\sigma_u \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_{eq} = \begin{cases} \sigma_{III}, & \text{when } \sigma_I > 0 \\ \sigma_{III} - \sigma_I, & \text{when } \sigma_I \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Figure 3: Schematic for definition of SCF

Considering that a transverse tensile strength is much lower than that of pure matrix material, a line averaged stress concentration factor is employed [5].

$$K_{22} = \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \frac{\sigma_{22}^m}{(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}} dr \quad (17)$$

where σ_{22}^m is the transverse stress in two-phase CCA model and the $(\sigma_{22}^m)_{BM}$ is the averaged transverse stress calculated by bridging model. In Equation (17), $b = a/\sqrt{V^f}$ in which “a” is the radius of constituent fiber.

4 COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENT DATA

To verify feasibility of the bridging tensor derived from an incremental Mori-Tanaka method, nonlinear behaviors as well as ultimate strengths of five typical UD composite, i.e. IM7/8511-7, T300/PR319, AS/Epoxy1, S2-Glass/Epoxy2 and E-Glass/MY750, are evaluated. Comparison between the predicted results and experiment data is made. Mechanical properties of constituent materials are shown in **Table 1-3**. All the experiment data are taken from Ref. [7]. Fiber volume fractions of all the 5 UD composites are 60%.

Comparison results for the five UD composites under longitudinal tension, longitudinal compression, transverse tension, transverse compression and in-plane shear are shown in Table 4. Further, the nonlinear behaviors of the composites subjected to transverse compression and in-plane shear are plotted in Figure 4-8.

In terms of interphase effects, numerical study of IM7/8511-7 with an assumed interphase under transverse compression is made and shown in Figures 9-10. As few experiment data for interphase or composites with interphase can be found in the literature, for the sake of numerical analysis the interphase parameters are assumed as $E^I = \gamma E^m$ and $\mu^I = 0.35$, where the superscript “I” denotes the interphase. Generally speaking, a volume fraction of interphase is small, being about 1% [8]. However, a small volume fraction might render less diversity in effects of interphase on composites. Thus volume fractions of 1% and 10% are selected respectively in the numerical study. The interphase is assumed to be linearly elastic and not failed over the whole load process.

Fiber type	IM7 Carbon	T300 Carbon	AS Carbon	S2 Glass	E Glass
Longitudinal modulus E_{11} (Gpa)	276	231	231	87	74
Transverse modulus E_{22} (Gpa)	19	15	15	87	74
In-plane shear modulus G_{12} (Gpa)	27	15	15	36	30.8
Transverse shear modulus G_{23} (Gpa)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Major Poisson's ratio μ_{12}	7	7	7	36	30.8
Longitudinal tension strength X_{Tf} (Mpa)	5180	2500	3500	2850	2150
Longitudinal compression strength X_{Cf} (Mpa)	3200	2000	3000	2450	1450
Longitudinal tensile failure strain ϵ_{Tf}	1.87	1.086	1.515	3.27	2.905
Longitudinal compression failure strain ϵ_{Cf}	1.16	0.869	1.298	2.82	1.959

Table 1: Mechanical properties of fibers

Matrix type	8511-7 epoxy	PR319 epoxy	Epoxy 1	Epoxy 2	MY7 50
Modulus E_m (Gpa)	4.08	0.95	3.2	3.2	3.35
Shear modulus E_{22} (Gpa)	1.478	0.35	1.2	1.2	1.24
Poisson's ratio μ_{12}	0.38	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35
Tension strength Y_{Tm} (Mpa)	99	70	85	73	80
Compression strength Y_{Cm} (Mpa)	130	130	120	120	120
Shear strength S_m (Mpa)	57	41	50	52	54
Tensile failure strain ϵ_{Tm} (%)	4.4	7.3	2.65	2.5	2.7
Compression failure strain ϵ_{Cm} (%)	9	13.6	3.75	5	5
Shear failure strain γ_m (%)	5.1	11.5	4.16	6	6

Table 2: Mechanical properties of matrices

Properties(MPa)	8511-7	PR319	Epoxy 1	Epoxy 2	MY750
Material Parameters at Tension					
$(\sigma_Y)_1$	10	53.77	34.17	30	40
$(\sigma_Y)_2$	20	64.38	37.74	40	50
$(\sigma_Y)_3$	30	74.95	41.33	45	55
$(\sigma_Y)_4$	40	80.25	44.31	50	60
$(\sigma_Y)_5$	50	85.54	46.91	55	65
$(\sigma_Y)_6$	60	90.82	50.14	60	70
$(\sigma_Y)_7$	80	96.10	52.82	65	75
$(\sigma_Y)_8$	99	103.48	57.15	73	80
$(E_T)_1$	4000	950	3200	3191	3361
$(E_T)_2$	3571	905	3050	2924	3333

$(E_T)_3$	3226	852	2210	2941	3333
$(E_T)_4$	2857	761	1187	2857	3125
$(E_T)_5$	2564	702	590	2778	2778
$(E_T)_6$	2222	620	458	2778	2632
$(E_T)_7$	1835	536	412	2500	2174
$(E_T)_8$	1484	432	296	2424	1724
Material Parameters at Tension					
$(\sigma_Y)_1$	20	32.77	50.83	50	50
$(\sigma_Y)_2$	30	38.09	55.05	60	60
$(\sigma_Y)_3$	40	43.36	59.50	70	70
$(\sigma_Y)_4$	60	48.59	63.91	80	80
$(\sigma_Y)_5$	80	53.69	68.28	90	90
$(\sigma_Y)_6$	100	58.67	72.54	100	100
$(\sigma_Y)_7$	120	63.55	74.63	110	110
$(\sigma_Y)_8$	130	65.98	76.69	120	120
$(E_T)_1$	4000	1862	6840	3205	3356
$(E_T)_2$	3740	1350	3410	3125	3226
$(E_T)_3$	3333	1241	3370	3125	3226
$(E_T)_4$	2532	1084	3010	2857	3030
$(E_T)_5$	1724	870	2687	2632	2632
$(E_T)_6$	1143	657	2255	2083	2041
$(E_T)_7$	781	464	1970	1538	1493
$(E_T)_8$	599	359	1745	1064	980

Table 3 Plastic parameters of the matrices

Five UD Composites		IM7 8511-7	T300 PR319	AS Epoxy1	S2-Glass Epoxy2	E-Glass MY750
Longitudinal tension	Experiment (MPa)	2560	1378	1990	1700	1280
	Prediction (MPa)	2867	1506	2114	1718	1310
	Error	12%	9%	6%	1%	2%
Longitudinal compression	Experiment (MPa)	1590	950	1500	1150	800
	Prediction (MPa)	1455	1208	1158	1502	898
	Error	-8%	27%	-23%	31%	12%
Transverse tension	Experiment (MPa)	73	40	38	63	40
	Prediction (MPa)	70	48	51	50	55
	Error	-4%	20%	34%	-21%	38%
Transverse compression	Experiment (MPa)	185	125	150	180	145
	Prediction (MPa)	175	145	149	164	163
	Error	-5%	16%	-1%	-9%	12%
Transverse shear	Experiment (MPa)	90	97	70	72	73
	Prediction (MPa)	67	55	44	80	84
	Error	-26%	-43%	-37%	11%	15%

Table 4: Comparison of measured and predicted strengths of 5 UD composites

Figure 4: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of IM7/8511-7 UD composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 5: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of T300/PR319 UD composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 6: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of AS/Epoxy 1 composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 7: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of S2-Glass/Epoxy 2 UD composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 8: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of E-Glass/MY750 UD composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 9: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of IM7/8511-7 UD with an interphase of 1% volume fraction ($E^I = \gamma E^m$, $\mu^I = 0.35$) composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

Figure 10: Comparison between measured and predicted stress-strain curves of IM7/8511-7 UD with an interphase of 10% volume fraction ($E^I = \gamma E^m$, $\mu^I = 0.35$) composite under transverse compression/in-plane shear

5 DISCUSSION

Based on an incremental Mori-Tanaka's method and Prandtl-Reuss theory, an incremental bridging model is established. In this model, nonlinear deformation of the composite is controlled by the plastic behaviour of the matrix. Non-linear behaviours of 5 typical UD composites are evaluated and results show that predictions are reasonably accurate compared with experimental data.

Regarding on transverse tension, it is frequently detected that failure occurs before a composite having significant nonlinear deformation. Thus a stress concentration factor is applied specifically to the transverse tension and great improvement on predicting accuracy is obtained. However, the prediction of transverse strength is still too high in some cases. This phenomenon is closely related to an interface strength that is hardly measurable by an experiment.

Assuming that the interphase keeps intact until a composite failure, numerical study on effects of the interphase on nonlinear behaviour of a composite under transverse compression is made. Numerical results show that a larger interphase volume fraction gives greater effects on a composite response. Further, diversity becomes more unobvious when interphase varies from soft to stiff.

6 CONCLUSIONS

An increment bridging model is established to predict nonlinear behaviour of fibrous composites, with the help of Mori-Tanaka method and Prandtl-Reuss plastic theory. Good agreement is obtained between experiment data and predicting results. Further, using the concept of equivalent fiber method, the effect of an interphase on a composite is studied numerically.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Financial supports from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant Nos. 11272238, 11472192) and Doctoral Fund of Ministry of Education of China (Grant No. 20120072110036) are acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z.M. Huang, Simulation of the mechanical properties of fibrous composites by the bridging micromechanics model, *Composites Part A*, **32**, 2001, pp. 143-172.
- [2] M. Zabihpoor, S. Adibnazari, A Micromechanics Approach for Fatigue of Unidirectional Fibrous Composites, *Iranian Polymer Journal*, **16**, 2007 pp. 219-232.
- [3] S. Ryan, M. Wicklein, A. Mouritz, W. Riedel, F. Schäfer, K. Thoma, Theoretical prediction of dynamic composite material properties for hypervelocity impact simulations. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*. **36**, 2009 pp. 899-912.
- [4] Rafic Younes, Ali Hallal, Farouk Fardoun and Fadi Hajj Chehade (2012). Comparative Review Study on Elastic Properties Modeling for Unidirectional Composite Materials, *Composites and Their Properties, Prof. Ning Hu (Ed.)*, ISBN: 978-953-51-0711-8, InTech, DOI: 10.5772/50362.
- [5] Z.M. Huang, L.Liu, Stress concentration factor in matrix of a composite reinforced with transversely isotropic fibres, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **48**, 2014, pp. 81-98.
- [6] Z.M. Huang, Y.X. Zhou, *Strength of Fibrous Composites*, Zhejiang University Press, Hangzhou, China, 2011.
- [7] A.S. Kaddour, M.J. Hinton, Input data for test cases used in benchmarking triaxial failure theories of composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **46**, 2012, pp.2295-2312.
- [8] Y. Benveniste, G.J. Dvorak, T. Chen, Stress fields in composites with coated inclusions, *Mechanics of Materials*. **7**, 1989 pp. 305-317.